

Publicaciones científicas revisadas por pares relacionadas a temática de Clima-UVG

1. Aguilar-Støen, M., Taylor, M., y Castellanos, E. (2016). Agriculture, land tenure and international migration in rural Guatemala. *Journal of Agrarian Change* 16(1): 123-144. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joac.12091>
2. Anchukaitis, K. J., Taylor, M. J., Martin-Fernández, J., Pons, D., Dell, M., Chopp, C., y Castellanos, E. J. (2013). Annual chronology and climate response in *Abies guatemalensis* Rehder (Pinaceae) in Central America. *The Holocene* 23(2): 270-277. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683612455548>
3. Anchukaitis, K. J., Taylor, M. J., Leland, C., Pons, D., Martin-Fernández, J., y Castellanos, E. J. (2014). Tree-ring reconstructed dry season rainfall in Guatemala. *Climate Dynamics* 43: 189-203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-014-2407-y>
4. Angelsen, A., Aguilar-Støen, M., Ainembabazi, J. H., Castellanos, E. J., y Taylor, M. J. (2020). Migration, remittances, and forest cover change in rural Guatemala and Chiapas, Mexico. *Land* 9(3): 88. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land9030088>
5. Ariano-Sánchez, D., Nesthus, A., Rosell, F. y Reinhardt, S. (2023). Developed black beaches – too hot to emerge? Factors affecting sand temperatures at nesting grounds of olive ridley sea turtles (*Lepidochelys olivacea*). *Climate Change Ecology* 5: 100074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecochg.2023.100074>
6. Asturias Schaub, L. R., & Gil-Alaña, L. A. (2026). Time series perspectives on North Atlantic tropical cyclones: A study of fractional integration patterns. *Natural Hazards*, 122(51). Springer. *Natural Hazards* (2026) 122:51 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-025-07793-0>
7. Asturias-Schaub, L. R., & Gil-Alana, L. A. (2023). CO₂ emissions in Latin America: A time series perspective based on fractional integration. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(50), 109585–109605. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. DOI: [10.1007/s11356-023-29987-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-29987-4)
8. Brincker, J. Fuentes, G. (2023). Análisis de brechas de capacidad y conocimiento en la evaluación de impactos, vulnerabilidades y riesgos del cambio climático, con énfasis en género, en el sector marino costero de Guatemala. *Revista UVG No.45*. Centro de Estudios Ambientales y Biodiversidad-Universidad del Valle de Guatemala. 14pp.
9. Castellanos, E. J. (2022a). Central America in dire need of inclusive climate resilient development with support from the international community. *PLOS Climate* 1(11): e0000105. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000105>
10. Castellanos, E. J., Lemos, M. F., Astigarraga, L., et al. (2022b). Central and South America. En H.-O. Pörtner et al. (Eds.), *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability (IPCC AR6 WGII)*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844.014>

11. Castellanos, E. J., Thomas, T. S., y Dunston, S. (2018). Climate change, agriculture, and adaptation options for Guatemala. International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI). Disponible en: <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/items/ae072d18-eb29-421f-abd1-cc279f240d03>
12. Castellanos, E., D. Fernández, D. Incer, J. Robb, A. Quilo, G. Alfaro, E. López, O. Regalado, G. Fuentes y D. Pons. (2017). Línea base de deforestación para iniciativas REDD+ en la región subnacional Sarstún-Motagua, Guatemala. *Revista Mesoamericana de Biodiversidad y Cambio Climático Yu'am* 2(3):48-54.
13. Castellanos, E. J., Tucker, C., Eakin, H., Morales, H., Barrera, J. F., y Díaz, R. (2013). Assessing the adaptation strategies of farmers facing multiple stressors: Lessons from the Coffee and Global Changes project in Mesoamerica. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 26, 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.07.003>
14. Castellanos, E., Díaz, R., Eakin, H., y Jiménez, G. (2008). Understanding the resources of small coffee growers within the global coffee chain through a livelihood analysis approach. En H. Tiessen y J. Stewart (Eds.), *Applying ecological knowledge to ecological decisions*. Scientific Committee on Problems of the Environment (SCOPE). Disponible en: https://www.iai.int/admin/site/sites/default/files/Applying_Ecological_Knowledge_to_Landuse_Decisions.pdf
15. Cavazos, T., Bettolli, M. L., Campbell, D., Sánchez Rodríguez, R. A., Mycoo, M., Arias, P. A., Rivera, J., Reboita, M. S., Gulizia, C., Hidalgo, H. G., Alfaro, E. J., Stephenson, T. S., Sörensson, A. A., Cerezo-Mota, R., Castellanos, E. J., Ley, D., y Mahon, R. (2024). Challenges for climate change adaptation in Latin America and the Caribbean region. *Frontiers in Climate*, 6, 1392033. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2024.1392033>
16. Cifuentes, M., Henry, M., Réjou-Méchain, M., Wayson, C., Zapata-Cuartas, M., Piotto, D., Alice Guier, F., Castañeda Lombis, H., Castellanos, E. J., et al. (2015a). Guidelines for documenting and reporting tree allometric equations. *Annals of Forest Science*, 72, 763–768. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-014-0415-z>
17. Cifuentes, M., Henry, M., Réjou-Méchain, M., López, O. R., Castellanos, E. J., et al. (2015b). Overcoming obstacles to sharing data on tree allometric equations. *Annals of Forest Science*, 72, 789–794. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-015-0467-8>
18. Díaz, R., Castellanos, E., y Jiménez, G. (2009). Condiciones para la adaptación de pequeños productores de café ante presiones económicas mediante procesos de “upgrading” en la cadena productiva. *Revista Iberoamericana de Economía Ecológica*, 10, 61–72. ISSN 13902776.
19. Eakin, H., Tucker, C., Castellanos, E. J., Díaz-Porras, R., Barrera, J. F., y Morales, H. (2013a). Adaptation in a multi-stressor environment: Perceptions and responses to climatic and economic risks by coffee growers in Mesoamerica. *Environment*,

Development and Sustainability, 15, 905–926. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-013-9466-9>

20. Eakin, H., Morales, H., Castellanos, E. J., Cruz-Bello, G., y Barrera, J. F. (2013b). Coffee, disasters and social–ecological resilience in Guatemala and Chiapas, Mexico. In S. Boulter et al. (Eds.), *Natural disasters and adaptation to climate change* (pp. 173–190). Cambridge University Press. doi:[10.1017/CBO9780511845710.023](https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511845710.023). Disponible en: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/288249558_Coffee_disasters_and_social-ecological_resilience_in_Guatemala_and_Chiapas_Mexico
21. Eakin, H., Bojórquez-Tapia, L. A., Díaz, R., Castellanos, E., y Hagggar, J. (2011). Adaptive capacity and social–environmental change: Theoretical and operational modeling of smallholder coffee systems response in the Mesoamerican Pacific Rim. *Environmental Management*, 47, 352–367. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-010-9603-2>
22. Eakin, H., C. Tucker y E. Castellanos. 2006. Responding to the coffee crisis: a pilot study of farmers’ adaptations in Mexico, Guatemala and Honduras. *The Geographical Journal* 172(2): 156-171.
23. Eakin, H., C. Tucker y E. Castellanos. 2005. Market Shocks and Climate Variability. The Coffee Crisis in Mexico, Guatemala, and Honduras. *Mountain Research and Development* 25(4): 304-309.
24. Evans, C., Cherrington, E. A., Carey, L., Limaye, A., Maharjan, S., Incer Nuñez, D. I., Anderson, E. R., Herndon, K., & Flores-Anderson, A. I. (2025). Evaluating global and national datasets in an ensemble approach to estimating carbon emissions as part of SERVIR’s CARbon Pilot. *Remote Sensing*, 17(24), 3975. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs17243975>
25. Fuentes, G. y E. Castellanos. (2017). Propuesta del marco de gobernanza del sistema MRV en Guatemala para el sector bosques y otros usos de la tierra. *Revista Mesoamericana de Biodiversidad y Cambio Climático Yu’am* 2(3): 55-59.
26. Gilmore, E. A., Wrathall, D., Adams, H., Buhaug, H., Castellanos, E. J., Hilmi, N., McLeman, R., Singh, C., y Adelekan, I. (2024). Defining severe risks related to mobility from climate change. *Climate Risk Management*, 44, 100601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2024.100601>
27. Guerra, A., Ramírez, M. (2021). IV Congreso Nacional de Cambio Climático en Guatemala y sus principales resultados. *Revista Mesoamericana de Biodiversidad y Cambio Climático Yu’am*, 5(2): 38-44.
28. Hagen, I., Huggel, C., Ramajo, L., Chacón, N., Ometto, J. P., Postigo, J. C., y Castellanos, E. J. (2022). Climate change-related risks and adaptation potential in Central and South America during the 21st century. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17, 033002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac5271>

29. Hannah, L., Donatti, C. I., Harvey, C. A., Alfaro, E., Rodríguez, D. A., Bouroncle, C., Castellanos, E. J., et al. (2017). Regional modeling of climate change impacts on smallholder agriculture and ecosystems in Central America. *Climatic Change*, 141, 29–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-016-1867-y>
30. Henry, C., J. Baker, B. Shaw, A. Kondash, B. Leiva, E. Castellanos, C. Wade, B. Lord, G. Van Houtven, J. Redmon. (2021). How will renewable energy development goals affect energy poverty in Guatemala? *Energy Economics* 104: 105665.
31. Henry, M., Cifuentes, M., Réjou-Méchain, M., Piotto, D., Castellanos, E. J., et al. (2015a). Recommendations for the use of tree models to estimate national forest biomass and assess their uncertainty. *Annals of Forest Science*, 72, 769–777. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-015-0465-x>
32. Henry, M., Réjou-Méchain, M., Cifuentes, M., Wayson, C., Piotto, D., Castellanos, E. J., et al. (2015b). An overview of existing and promising technologies for national forest monitoring. *Annals of Forest Science*, 72, 779–788. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-015-0463-z>
33. Incer, D. (2020). Sensibilidad ambiental a la degradación de tierras de la meseta central de Guatemala. *Revista UVG No. 40*, (40), 77–88.
34. Iñiguez-Gallardo, V., D. Campbell, E. Castellanos y 7 autores. (2023). Place-based capacity building to enhance resilience in tropical countries. *One Earth* 6(8):935-938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2023.07.012>
35. Klein, J. A., Tucker, C., Castellanos, E. J., et al. (2019a). An integrated community and ecosystem-based approach to disaster risk reduction in mountain systems. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 94, 143–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.12.034>
36. Klein, J., et al. (2019b). Catalyzing transformations to sustainability in the world's mountains. *Earth's Future*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018EF001024>
37. Ley, D., Guillén Bolaños, T., Castañeda, A., Hidalgo, H. G., Girot, P. O., Fernández, R., Alfaro, E. J., y Castellanos, E. J. (2023). Central America urgently needs to reduce the growing adaptation gap to climate change. *Frontiers in Climate*, 5, 1215062. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2023.1215062>
38. Magrin, G. O., Marengo, J. A., Castellanos, E. J., et al. (2014). Central and South America. En V. R. Barros et al. (Eds.), *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability (IPCC AR5 WGII)*. Cambridge University Press. Disponible en: https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/02/WGIIAR5-Chap27_FINAL.pdf
39. Montenegro, R., y Castellanos, E. J. (2008). Dinámica forestal en seis bosques comunitarios comparada con la dinámica forestal observada en los respectivos municipios. *Revista de la UVG No. 17*, 70–78. Disponible en:

<https://repositorio.uvg.edu.gt/bitstreams/fda11d71-5a91-4b0f-98bf-a88ac136c4a0/download>

40. Olivares, J., Centeno, S. P., Quiroz, V., y Castellanos, E. J. (2023). Información climática disponible y recomendaciones para su uso en la inversión pública en los países del COSEFIN/SICA. CEPAL. Disponible en: <https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/707e88d9-7ec8-446b-ae92-2e040a0a6a11/content>
41. Paulson, M. E., Evans, T., Andersson, K., y Castellanos, E. J. (2014). Decentralization, forest management, and forest conditions in Guatemala. *Journal of Land Use Science*, 9, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1747423X.2014.915350>
42. Pons, D., Taylor, M. J., Griffin, D., Castellanos, E. J., y Anchukaitis, K. J. (2016). On the production of climate information in the high mountain forests of Guatemala. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 106, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2016.1235481>
43. Pons, D., Castellanos, E., Conde, D., Brincker, J., Incer, D., y López, A. (2018). *Escenarios de aridez para Guatemala para los años 2030, 2050 y 2070 utilizando modelos de cambio climático*. *Revista Mesoamericana de Biodiversidad y Cambio Climático Yu'am*, 2(4), 4–16. Disponible en: <https://revistayuam.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Art%C3%ADculo-cient%C3%ADfico-UVG-Aridez-1.pdf>
44. Quesada-Román, A., O. Calvo-Solano, D. Cruz-García, E. Castellanos, D. Ley y O. Vásquez. 2026. Unveiling historical data and socioeconomic drivers of disaster risk at national and municipal levels in Guatemala. *Discover Hazards* 2:7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44475-026-00015-6>
45. Ramos-Castillo, A., Castellanos, E. J., y Galloway McLean, K. (2017). Indigenous peoples, local communities and climate change mitigation. *Climatic Change*, 140(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-016-1873-0>
46. Ramos, C. E., Castellanos, E. J., y Restrepo, C. (2012). The transfer of modern organic carbon by landslide activity in tropical montane ecosystems. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*, 117(G03016). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JG001838>
47. Robb, J., Haggard, J., Lamboll, R., y Castellanos, E. (2019). Exploring the value–action gap through shared values, capabilities and deforestation behaviours in Guatemala. *Environmental Conservation*, 46(3), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892919000067>
48. Schmitt-Harsh, M., Evans, T. P., Castellanos, E. J., y Randolph, J. C. (2012). Carbon stocks in coffee agroforests and mixed dry tropical forests in the western highlands of Guatemala. *Agroforestry Systems*, 86, 141–157. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-012-9549-x>

49. Solano, A., D. Pons, C. Tucker, R. Díaz, J. Barrera, H. Eakin, y E. Castellanos. (2017). Biodiversity, sustainable certifications and climate change adaptation: lessons from shade coffee systems in Mesoamerica. En: *The Lima declaration on biodiversity and climate change. Convention on Biological Diversity, Technical Series No. 89*, Montreal, 156 pages.
50. Taylor, M. J., Aguilar-Støen, M., Castellanos, E., Moran-Taylor, M. J., y Gerkina, K. (2016). International migration, land use change and the environment in Ixcán, Guatemala. *Land Use Policy*, 54, 290–301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.02.024>
51. Taylor, M., Moran-Taylor, M., Castellanos, E., y Elías, S. (2011). Burning for sustainability: Biomass energy, international migration, and the move to cleaner fuels and cook stoves in Guatemala. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 101(4), 1–11. [doi:10.1080/00045608.2011.568881](https://doi.org/10.1080/00045608.2011.568881)
52. Tucker, C. M., Eakin, H., y Castellanos, E. J. (2010). Perceptions of risk and adaptation: Coffee producers, market shocks, and extreme weather in Central America and Mexico. *Global Environmental Change*, 20(1), 23–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2009.07.006>
53. Tucker, C., Randolph, J. C., y Castellanos, E. (2007). Institutions, biophysical factors and history: An integrative analysis of private and common property forests in Guatemala and Honduras. *Human Ecology*, 35, 259–274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19186444.2010.11658221>
54. Vásquez, W.F., Villagrán, X., & Leiva, B. (2025). Electrification of boat tours: preferences of foreign and domestic tourists in Guatemala. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, doi:[10.1080/09640568.2025.2564223](https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2025.2564223).
55. Villagrán, X., Vásquez, W. F., & Leiva, B. (2025). Tourist preferences for cleaner mobility: A contingent valuation of electric rickshaws in Guatemala. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*, 1–12. doi:[10.1080/15568318.2025.2499037](https://doi.org/10.1080/15568318.2025.2499037).